

dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A values against 'B' (pH meter readings). The curve extends over a range of $0.37 < \bar{n}_A < 1.83$ and is wavelike (Fig. 1). The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H

Fig. 1. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene monoethanolamine formation curve.

were determined from the half integral points at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. These values were also corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs B and $\log(2 - \bar{n}_A/\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs B. Formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria were obtained from the plots of \bar{n} vs pL (Fig. 2). From these, the values of the stability constants $\log K_1$ were calculated at $\bar{n} = 0.5$. These values were further corroborated by the plot of $\log(\bar{n}/1 - \bar{n})$ vs pL.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene monoethanolamine formation curves.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stabilities of trivalent metal chelates is $Pr^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Gd^{3+}$.

If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E = Z^2/2r(1 - \frac{1}{D})$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge 'Z' and

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cations	$t = 25^\circ$					
	H^+	Pr^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Y^{3+}
$\log K_1$	11.05	14.10	10.90	11.12	11.90	11.06
$\log K_2$	8.45	—	—	—	—	—

radius 'r' in a medium of dielectric constant 'D'. Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the log K values should increase linearly with Z^2/r .

The plots of log K against Z^2/r tend to diverge widely as regards a linear relationship. The results are similar to those reported by Khanolkar and Ingle⁴ who explain these deviations on the basis that the assumption regarding the ionic character of the metal-ligand bond may not be valid. The deviations may be accounted for by the increased covalent nature of the bonding in the rare earth complexes, where the ligands have N and O atoms as the donor set.

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Complexes of Mono- and Di-tertiaryphosphine Sulphides or Selenides with Zinc(II) and Mercury(II)

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VERY few complexes of zinc(II) with mono- and di-tertiaryphosphine sulphides are known¹⁻³. There is no adduct of a corresponding phosphine selenide with any zinc(II) salt. However, in contrast to

TABLE—THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Found(%)		Required(%)		Dec. Pt. °C	ν P-C, cm^{-1}	Molar conductance $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
		C	H	C	H			
1.	ZnI ₂ .Ph ₃ PSe	32.88	2.15	32.73	2.27	240 ^a	1105	17.70
2.	ZnI ₂ .PDPSe	36.95	3.03	36.44	2.92	262-63	1120	14.58
3.	ZnI ₂ .PDPS	38.40	3.13	40.75	3.27	248-53	1125	16.20
4.	HgCl ₂ .T ₃ PSe	38.27	3.18	38.47	3.21	205-20	1120	3.56
5.	HgBr ₂ .T ₃ PSe	34.06	2.85	33.87	2.82	225-38	1125	4.75
6.	HgI ₂ .T ₃ PSe	30.54	2.56	30.07	2.52	215	1125	3.78
7.	Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .2Ph ₃ PS	45.89	3.24	47.31	3.28	250	1120	14.65
8.	3Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .4Ph ₃ PSe	36.03	2.76	36.94	2.57	235-45	1125	Insoluble

(a) The complex melts.

zinc(II), mercury(II) is known to form relatively more number of complexes with these type of ligands⁴⁻¹⁴. In the present communication, we are reporting adducts of zinc(II) iodide, with triphenylphosphine selenide (Ph₃PSe), 1,3-propylene bis(diphenylphosphine selenide) (PDPSe) and 1,3-propylene bis(diphenylphosphine sulphide) (PDPS); mercury(II) halides with tri-*p*-tolylphosphine selenide (T₃PSe) and mercury(II) nitrate with triphenylphosphine sulphide (Ph₃PS) and triphenylphosphine selenide.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by the reaction of corresponding tertiaryphosphines with sulphur powder or elemental selenium in dry benzene under reflux followed by recrystallization from benzene-alcohol mixture^{1,5}.

Mercury halide complexes were obtained by mixing solutions of corresponding halide in ethanol and the ligand in benzene or a mixture of ethanol-benzene followed by refluxing. Mercury nitrate complexes were obtained by treating nitrate solution and ligand solution in acetone at room temperature (~25-30°). Zinc iodide complexes were obtained from mixing of iodide solution in diethyl ether and the ligand in benzene followed by refluxing. The complex either separates during refluxing or by adding petroleum-ether (40-60°) after concentration. Metal salts and solvents were dry and of reagent grade.

The elemental analysis was carried out by Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne. The infrared spectra was recorded with Spektromom 2000 instrument. Molar conductance in nitrobenzene was determined with a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge Type CLO1/02.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of the metal salts with ligands were carried out in the ratio of 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) in suitable solvents. The adducts obtained are 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) in case of zinc(II) iodide and

mercury(II) halides, while 1 : 2 (Ph₃PS) and 3 : 4 adducts (Ph₃PSe) are obtained in case of mercury(II) nitrate. All the complexes are stable and normally white crystalline solids. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and normally decompose above the melting points of the ligands. The elemental analyses, melting and decomposition points of complexes, molar conductance and phosphorus-carbon_(aromatic) stretching frequencies for complexes are given in the Table. The molar conductance in nitrobenzene shows partial dissociation of the adducts in the solvent.

The infrared spectra in the range 4600-650 cm^{-1} excludes the presence of water in the complexes. The phosphorus-carbon_(aromatic) stretching frequencies at 1120 cm^{-1} in the free ligands remain almost unaffected as a result of coordination through 'S' or 'Se' donor atoms in the complexes excepting the complex (I) in the Table which records a fall of 15 cm^{-1} . A similar behaviour has been observed earlier^{1,8,14}. The nitrate group in Hg(NO₃)₂.2(Ph₃PS) complex shows infrared bands at 1400(s), 1300(s), 825(m) and 760(m) cm^{-1} and that in 3Hg(NO₃)₂.4Ph₃PSe at 1390(s), 1265(m), 1075(m), 960(m) and 820(w) cm^{-1} . The bands due to nitrate in 700-750 cm^{-1} region appear to have been obscured by the phenyl bands of the ligands. The infrared spectra and molar conductance are indicative of covalent nature of nitrate groups. The further work on these and related complexes is in progress.

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Complexes of Neodymium(III) with Glycine, Iminodiacetic Acid and Nitrilotriacetic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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AMINO acids have been extensively used for the complex formation with various metals¹⁻⁵. Among the amino acids the chelating ability of the derivatives of acetic acid is particularly noteworthy. In recent years, rare earth complexes with various complexing agents have been studied employing pH titration, potentiometric and spectrophotometric techniques etc⁶⁻⁹. However, little attention has been given on the polarographic study of the rare earth complexes. In the present communication the authors have reported the polarographic study of Nd(III) complexes with glycine, iminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acids.

Experimental

Stock solutions of 0.01 M glycine (E. merck, Germany), iminodiacetic acid (BDH) and nitrilotriacetic acid (Reanal, Hungary) were prepared in carbon dioxide free double distilled water. The Nd(III) solution was prepared by dissolving a calculated quantity of the metal oxide in minimum amount of dil. hydrochloric acid (AnalaR). The metal solution was standardised by EDTA method¹⁰.

Potassium chloride 2.0 M and gelatin (AnalaR), solution were prepared in double distilled water.

A preliminary experimental set was prepared by keeping overall concentration of potassium chloride, gelatin and Nd(III) fixed at 1.0 M, 0.01% and 2 m M respectively. In the other sets, in addition to the above metal ion, supporting electrolyte and gelatin concentrations, the ligand concentration was varied from 0.25 m M to 3.0 m M. The ionic strength was fixed at 1.0 by adjusting with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid was used to fix the pH value of the solution at 2.75 ± 0.02.

Current-Voltage curves were obtained by using a C.I.C (Baroda, India) polarograph, the capillary used had m value of 2.15 mg/sec, and drop time of 3.1 sec/drop at -1.765 V vs SCE, when measured in an air free 1.0 M KCl solution at 45 cm of effective height of mercury ($m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$). Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing purified nitrogen gas through the solutions and the polarograms were recorded. For adjusting pH at 2.75 ± 0.02 an Elico digital pH meter was used. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature 32 ± 0.1°.

Results and Discussion

Nd(III) gives a well defined reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M potassium chloride plus 0.01% gelatin at pH 2.75¹¹⁻¹². The reduction of Nd(III) and Nd(III)-complexes with all the three ligands were found to be of diffusion controlled nature as the plots of i vs \sqrt{h} ($\sqrt{\text{effective height of mercury column}}$) yielded straight lines passing through the origin. An analysis of the plots of E_{dme} vs $\log I/1d-I$ and $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ values for the simple Nd(III) and for its complexes with all the three ligands i.e., (substituted amino gr. derivatives of acetic acid) revealed a reversible nature of the reduction waves.

Effect of Ligand Concentration :

At pH 2.75 the half wave potential of Nd(III) shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of ligands.

A Lingane¹³ treatment of the data revealed 1 : 1 complexes of Nd(III) with all the three ligands e.g., glycine, iminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid. The metal ligand ratio and the values of the stability constants have been tabulated below.

TABLE

Stability Constants of Nd(III) Complexes

1. Nd(III)-Glycine	$\log \beta$	4.00
2. Nd(III)-Iminodiacetic acid	$\log \beta$	4.36
3. Nd(III)-Nitrilotriacetic acid	$\log \beta$	4.78